

Search for New Antiviral Agents. Part. I. Synthesis of Aryl Sulfamoyl Benzamido Alkyl/Aralkyl Esters

VINAY S. MISRA and MANJU VARSHNEYA

Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University, Lucknow

Manuscript received 1 June 1974; revised 26 August 1974; accepted 27 August 1974

A number of aryl sulfamoyl benzamido alkyl/aralkyl esters have been synthesised with a view to study their antiviral properties.

VARIOUS amino acids have been claimed to increase the survival time of mice infected with different viruses¹⁻⁷. Numerous sulfonamides of diversified chemical constitution exhibit significant anti-viral activity both against plant as well as animal viruses⁸⁻¹¹.

In view of these varied observations we have synthesised fourteen novel sulfonamide derivatives incorporating the well known anti-viral peptide linkage or moiety expecting an increase in the anti-viral potency of sulfonamides.

Aryl sulfamoyl benzamido aryl/alkyl esters were prepared by condensing an appropriate aryl sulfamoyl benzoyl chloride with the corresponding amino acid esters. The steps involved in the synthesis are

Aryl sulfamoyl benzamido aryl/aralkyl esters

In a 50 ml R.B. flask equipped with a reflux condenser, a mechanical stirrer, a dropping funnel and a calcium chloride guard tube were placed aryl-sulfamoyl benzoyl chloride (0.011 mole) and absolute ethanol (20 ml). The solution of an appropriate amino acid (0.01 mole) in absolute ethanol was gradually introduced into the above solution under constant stirring and the mixture refluxed for 2-3 hrs. The solution was then concentrated and cooled and the separated solid was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

The title compounds (I) obtained in a 60-70% yield are summarised in Table 1.

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected.

Amino acid esters and aryl sulfamoyl benzoyl chlorides were prepared by adopting the methods of Darapsky and Prabhakar¹² and Ullmann and Bleier¹³ and Curtius¹⁴.

The anti-viral screening of these compounds is in progress at Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow and the findings shall be shortly published.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Dr. Nitya Nand, Deputy Director, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow

TABLE I

Sl. No.	α	R	R'	m.p. °C	Molecular Formula	% N	
						Obsd.	Calcd.
1.	1	H	CH ₃	90	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₅ S	7.20	7.49
2.	1	H	H	100	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₅ S	7.80	7.70
3.	α .1	CH ₃	CH ₃	70	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₅ S	6.90	7.18
4.	α .1	CH ₃	H	85	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₅ S	8.20	7.44
5.	β .2	CH ₃	CH ₃	75	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₅ S	7.19	7.18
6.	β .2	CH ₃	H	60	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₅ S	8.01	7.44
7.	1	-CH ₂	CH ₃	101	C ₂₅ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₆ S	5.09	5.81
8.	1	-H ₂ C	H	100	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₆ S	5.77	5.99
9.	1	-CH ₂ COOH	CH ₃	90	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₅ S	6.03	6.19
10.	1	-CH ₂ COOH	H	85	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₅ S	6.23	6.38
11.	1	-CH ₂ CH ₂ COOH	CH ₃	67	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₅ S	5.03	5.92
12.	1	-CH ₂ CH ₂ COOH	H	78	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₅ S	6.01	6.07
13.	1	-CH ₂	CH ₃	83	C ₂₅ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₅ S	5.95	6.16
14.	1	-CH ₂	H	63	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₅ S	6.03	6.37

for microanalysis and Prof. Ram Gopal, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University for providing necessary departmental facilities. One of us (M.V.) is grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of a junior research fellowship.

References

1. R. L. THOMPSON and A. R. LAVENDER, *Proc. Soc. Exptl. Biol.*, 1953, 84, 483.
2. L. DICKINSON and M. J. THOMPSON, *Brit. J. Pharmacol.*, 1957, 12, 66.
3. M. W. PONS and W. S. PRESTON, *Virology*, 1961, 15, 164.
4. M. D. EATON, B. MAGASANK, M. E. PERRY and D. KARIBIAN, *Proc. Soc. Exptl. Biol. Med.*, 1951, 77, 505.
5. W. W. ACKERMANN, A. RABSON and H. KURZ, *J. Exptl. Med.*, 1954, 100, 437.
6. M. A. STAHMANN, L. H. GRAF, S. E. L. PATTEBSON, J. C. WALKER and D. W. WATSON, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1951, 189, 45.
7. J. R. RUBINI, A. R. RASMUSSEN Jr., and M. A. STAHMANN, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1951, 189, 662.
8. G. JOHANN and D. MARTIN, *Brit. Patent*, Nov. 1972, 12,980,57.
9. H. E. KAUFMAN, *N.Y. Ann. Acad. Sci.*, 1965, 130, 163.
10. M. L. HOEFFE and A. HOLMES, *Ger. Offen*, Jan. 1972, 2,132,987.
11. T. SUIGESHI, K. S. TOYODO, T. S. TADASHI, *Ger. Offen*, 11 March 1971, 2,043,933.
12. A. DARAPSKY and M. PRABHAKAR, *Ber.*, 1912, 45, 1664.
13. F. ULLMANN and H. BLEIER, *Ber.* 1902, 35, 4274
14. U. G. CURTIUS, *J. für Pr. Chemie.*, 2, 37, 159.